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3 **Retinal image recognition for verifying the identity of fattening and**
4 **replacement lambs¹**

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14 **ABSTRACT:** With the objective of verifying the presumed identity of sheep in a
15 traceability study based on visual ear tags and electronic boluses, retinal image
16 recognition was used as an auditing biomarker on 152 lambs of 2 dairy breeds
17 (Manchega, n = 82; Lacaune, n = 70). Lambs were identified with temporary ear tags
18 (birth to weaning), and with official ear tags and electronic mini-boluses (weaning to

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19 yearling). At 3-mo of age, 58 lambs were recruited for flock replacement, and the rest
20 were transported to a slaughterhouse. Retinal images (RI) and capturing times (CT)
21 were recorded from the left and right eye of each lamb by duplicate and by the same
22 operator using an OptiReader device (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO) at 3, 6 and 12 mo of
23 age in 152, 58 and 58 lambs, respectively. The 3-mo RI were used as reference images
24 and to assess operator training and accuracy of the technique. Intra- and inter-age
25 comparisons were made to obtain the matching score (MS, 0 to 100) of pairs of RI from
26 the same eye, using Optibrand's software. Operator skill improved with training
27 sessions but MS reached a plateau after the 6th session (264 images; MS = 93.2 ± 1.5).
28 Values of CT also decreased in trained compared to untrained operator (63 ± 5 vs. 144 ±
29 15 s, respectively; $P < 0.001$). Training data were eliminated from further analysis.
30 Matching exclusion criteria was estimated from trained operator images at random (804
31 images) using a non-parametric receiver operating characteristic curve analysis for MS
32 = 70. No breed, eye or age effects were detected in the MS intra-age comparisons at 3-,
33 6- and 12-mo periods, which averaged 96.3 ± 0.3. Capturing time was longer in
34 Lacaune than in Manchega lambs ($P < 0.01$) and decreased by age (34 ± 4 and 21 ± 2 s,
35 for 6- and 12-mo periods, respectively; $P < 0.001$). Regarding lamb traceability, 2.8%
36 temporary ear tags were lost from birth to weaning (traceability, 97.2%) but no official
37 ear tag or mini-bolus losses were reported from weaning to yearling (traceability,
38 100%). Inter-age MS comparison, used as the biomarker for traceability auditing, did
39 not vary by age or breed, on average being 92.6 ± 0.5. Using the 3-mo RI as reference,
40 all 6- and 12-mo RI showed MS > 70 which supported 100% lamb traceability. In
41 conclusion, retinal imaging was an accurate technique for auditing the identity of living
42 lambs from weaning to yearling.

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44 **Key words:** animal identification, biometry, retinal image, sheep, traceability

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INTRODUCTION

47 Meat traceability is a complex (i.e., from birth to retail sales) and incompletely
48 solved process (Arana et al., 2002; Caja et al., 2002) requiring the use of identification
49 (**ID**) devices and of auditing systems (McKean, 2001, Caja et al., 2002). Current
50 livestock ID range from visual to electronic devices but biometrics (e.g., genetic
51 fingerprinting and retinal imaging) have been proposed to overcome the main
52 limitations of ID devices and for auditing (Caja et al., 2004; Felmer et al., 2006; Barry
53 et al., 2008).

54 The use of retinal images (**RI**) is based on the uniqueness and invariability of the
55 retinal vascular pattern of each eye. Completion of retina at birth varies according to
56 specie precocity, individuals and diseases (Flowers et al., 1985; Hellström et al., 2002).
57 First results point out that sheep clones can be differentiated by RI (Whittier et al.,
58 2003). Barry et al. (2008) reported slight changes in the curvature of retinal vessels of
59 Irish crossbred lambs from 1 to 22 wk of age which did not affect the matching score
60 (**MS**) of the RI comparisons between ages. Nevertheless, MS is not a continuous
61 variable and previous data transformation is required before statistical analysis (Puig et
62 al., 2009). This data transformation was not done in the study by Barry et al. (2008)
63 which made uncertain some of their results. Moreover, there is no information on RI
64 analyses for longer periods, as well as left and right eye relationship and breed effect.

65 The objective of this study was to verify the presumed identity of sheep traced from
66 weaning to yearling by ear tags and electronic boluses, using RI as the auditing
67 biomarker. The adequate discrimination threshold for the effective matching of pairs of
68 RI, the required length of the operator training period and the repeatability of the

69 methodology between eye duplicates and ages was also investigated in 2 breeds of
70 sheep differing in precocity. A specific model for the treatment of matching score data
71 from RI was also developed.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

74 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the
75 Ethical Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation (Reference CEEAH 656/07)
76 of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra, Barcelona. Spain).

77

Animals, Rearing and Management

78 *Animals, Rearing and Management*

79 Manchega and Lacaune weaned lambs (approximately 1 mo of age, 11.5 ± 0.2 kg
80 BW) born at the Experimental Farm of the SIGCE (Servei de Granges i Camps
81 Experimentals, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bellaterra, Spain), were used.
82 Manchega and Lacaune are dairy sheep breeds from Spain and France, respectively,
83 differing in precocity, growth speed and milk yield, but of similar adult frame and BW
84 (Marie et al., 2002; Flores et al., 2008). Lambs were intensively fed with a commercial
85 growth-fattening concentrate (NE_F , 1.90 Mcal/kg; CP, 17.4%; as fed), barley straw and
86 water ad libitum. A total of 152 lambs (Manchega, $n = 82$; Lacaune, $n = 70$) reached the
87 harvesting weight as Spanish ‘Recental’ lambs (approximately 3 mo of age, >23 kg
88 BW) and were slaughtered ($n = 94$; Manchega, $n = 54$; Lacaune, $n = 40$) or chosen for
89 replacement of the breeding flock ($n = 58$; Manchega, $n = 28$; Lacaune, $n = 30$).
90 Replacement ewe-lambs joined the adult flock at 28 kg of BW and grazed (6 h/d) Italian
91 ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.) as a group and were complemented indoors
92 according to their requirements. Replacement ram-lambs were reared separately and fed
93 according to their requirements.

94 ***Animal Identification***

95 All lambs were identified with official temporary (lambs traced as a group intended
96 for slaughter) and permanent (lamb individually traced and for replacement) ID devices,
97 according to European Union regulations (EC 21/2004; amended by EC 933/2008) and
98 current Spanish legislation (Real Decreto 947/2005; amended by 1486/2009). The
99 temporary ear tags were inserted at birth in the middle of the left ear of the lambs and
100 consisted of 2 rectangular flags made of polyurethane with a tamper-proof (pin and cup)
101 male-female closing system (2.8 g, 40 × 14.5 mm; Allflex-Azasa, Madrid, Spain).
102 Lambs were also identified at weaning (1 mo of age) with permanent official ear tags
103 attached to the right ear and with electronic mini-boluses recorded with the same
104 individual code.

105 The permanent ear tags had triangular flags made of polyurethane, which were laser
106 recorded and a tamper-proof (pin and cup) male-female closing system (5.2 g; 38 × 39
107 mm; Allflex-Azasa, Madrid, Spain). The electronic mini-boluses (19 g, 56.2 × 11.9 mm;
108 Allflex-Azasa, Madrid, Spain) contained a standardized 32 × 3.8-mm half-duplex
109 transponder recorded with a 16-digit code according to the current Spanish legislation
110 (Real Decreto 947/2005; amended by 1486/2009) and with ISO 11784 and 11785
111 standards on animal electronic ID (ISO, 1996, 2009). Boluses were administered by a
112 trained operator using an adapted balling gun (Rumitag, Espluges de Llobregat,
113 Barcelona, Spain) as described by Ghirardi et al. (2007).

114 Temporary official ear tags for lambs intended for harvesting were removed at 6 mo
115 of age, when replacement lambs joined the breeding flock, and were replaced by the
116 management ID ear tags of the farm.

117

118 ***Retinal Images***

119 The RI were obtained using the OptiReader device (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO), a
120 commercially available device designed for capturing retinal vascular images in
121 animals. The OptiReader device included a video fundus camera able to capture RI
122 pictures and any other digital image, and a controller with keyboard, screen and an
123 embedded Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver. The controller is a central
124 processing unit that works with the camera to capture and store the RI and other
125 information. The OptiReader device links the images captured with the location, exact
126 time and date, all set by the GPS receiver.

127 All RI were captured in duplicate and by the same operator in morning sessions,
128 done thrice a week, with 3 to 17 lambs (9.2 ± 1.1 lambs on average), inside a barn and
129 under natural daylight conditions. The operator was novel in RI capture, but
130 experienced in sheep management and restraint, and previously subjected to a short
131 theoretical and practical course (3 d length) for obtaining the main quality standards
132 required for a novice operator according to the Optibrand operator benchmarks (i.e.,
133 collecting only high quality RI with a MS > 85 between duplicates and demonstrated
134 thorough understanding of how the OptiReader device worked). Nevertheless, the
135 average proficiency criterion (time for acquiring RI < 1 min per eye) was not fulfilled,
136 which was used to evaluate the operator's skill progression without compromising the
137 RI quality.

138 Lambs were restrained in a self-closing head locker and the operator immobilized the
139 animal head with one hand, while handling the camera with the other. After setting the
140 location, time and data via the GPS receiver, the operator typed the permanent ear tag
141 ID number into the keyboard of the OptiReader and took a first picture of the ear tag
142 located on the side of the corresponding eye. Left eyes were processed before right eyes.
143 The device automatically captured the best quality RI (e.g. minimum glare and proper

144 focus) according to previously configured parameters on the controller (i.e. animal
145 specie, sheep; targeting selectivity, 0). After targeting activation, the camera was
146 directed at the lamb's eye, positioned at approximately 1 cm from the eye and an angle
147 of 45°, pointing toward the base of the animal's opposite ear, according to
148 recommendations of the manufacturer (Optibrand). The camera had a light source which
149 illuminated the fundus of the eye (ocular fundus) and allowed the visualization of the
150 retinal vascular pattern on the controller's screen (Figure 1). A RI was considered
151 acceptable when it showed a contrasted vascular pattern and vertical and horizontal
152 alignment in relation to the screen guidelines, and when there were no black edges,
153 glare, obstructions or blurriness, as reported in the OptiReader device user guide
154 (Optibrand).

155 In addition to GPS coordinates, date, time (to the nearest 0.1 s) and ear tag picture,
156 the capturing time (**CT**) was also recorded by the device and used to evaluate the
157 operator proficiency. The CT was measured to the nearest 10^{-3} s elapsed between
158 targeting activation and capture of an RI of acceptable quality. This time included the
159 several attempts done until obtaining an acceptable RI.

160 Recorded RI and associated data were stored on a 64 Mb compact flash memory card
161 (SanDisk, Shoot & Store Card, Milpitas, CA) in the form of encrypted binary large
162 object (so called blob) files, and transferred to a central database on-line supported by
163 using the Data Management software v. 4.1.3 of Optibrand. Uploaded RI were viewed
164 as "jpeg" files and used for subsequent matching trials of pairs of images. The
165 Optibrand software matching process used an implemented matching algorithm based
166 on the degree of similarity, size, position and branch angles of retinal vessels designed
167 to perform about 20 pairs of matches per minute (Allen et al., 2008). The Optibrand's
168 Data Management software overlaps the images to compute a MS which ranged

169 between 0 and 100. The higher the score, the more likely the images in the pair are from
170 the same eye.

171 In order to determine when the operator was proficient enough to obtain RI of
172 quality, thereby being considered as a trained operator according the Optibrand
173 benchmarks criteria (novice operator), the first RI taken from approximately the half of
174 the lambs at 3 mo of age (33 lambs from each breed, 264 images in total) was used.
175 Training data were analyzed separately from the rest of RI taken during the experiment.

176 A minimum MS threshold was determined as matching decision criteria. With this
177 aim, 2 series of one-to-one comparisons of pairs of RI (excluding the data used for
178 studying the training period) were carried out for determining the sensitivity (true
179 positives) and the specificity (true negatives) of the technique. A set of true match
180 comparisons was selected (404 pairs of RI) from different duplicates of the same eye
181 taken at 3, 6 and 12 mo of age. Further, a set of false pairs was selected (400 pairs of
182 RI) from images of eyes of different lambs chosen at random.

183 A total of 608 RI were collected from 152 lambs of 3 mo of age (2 images from both
184 eyes) which were used as reference for further analysis. The replacement lambs were re-
185 imaged at 6 and 12 mo (464 images).

186 Intra- and inter-age comparisons of pairs of RI for each eye were made, thereby
187 obtaining 1 intra-age (duplicates) and 4 inter-age (3 vs. 6 mo, and 3 vs. 12 mo taking
188 into account the duplicates) MS for each eye. Intra-age comparisons of pairs of RI were
189 used to setup the working methodology and to evaluate operator training, whereas inter-
190 age comparisons were used to audit the lamb identity assessed by ear tags and electronic
191 mini-boluses for lamb traceability.

192

193 ***Statistical Analyses***

194 Matching score threshold was determined by means of a non-parametric receiver
195 operating characteristic (**ROC**) curve analysis using the ROC procedure of SPSS v.
196 17.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). The ROC curve is a graphical method, extensively used
197 for assessing the characteristics of a diagnostic test where the true positive rate
198 (sensitivity) is plotted against the false positive rate (1-specificity) for different cut-off
199 points. Each point on the ROC plot represents a sensitivity/specificity pair for a decision
200 threshold.

201 Before the statistical analysis, the MS data were expressed as a proportion variable
202 ranging between 0 and 1 and were analyzed in order to identify their distribution profile.
203 An excess of values equal to 1 (MS = 100) were observed in the MS data, indicating
204 that the distribution did not correspond to the profile of a continuous distribution such
205 as the Beta or the Logistic-normal distributions. Consequently, for analyzing this
206 semicontinuous data, the one-inflated bivariate Beta distribution was used, building a
207 specific model for the treatment of MS data from RI. Parameter estimation was done by
208 maximizing the corresponding log-likelihood function using a program made in R free
209 computing software (www.r-project.org; see Appendix). Similar zero-inflated Beta
210 models have been recently used for analyzing proportions in finances (Cook et al.,
211 2008).

212 To compare the inter-age images used for identity verification and for auditing the
213 traceability, we also considered random effects models. The models have the special
214 feature of the excess of 1's (one-inflated Beta model terms). Logarithmic
215 transformations (\log_{10}) for CT data were done. Least square means of CT were obtained
216 with the MIXED procedure of SAS (v. 9.1, SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC) according to a
217 split-plot model (whole plot = breed, subplot = eye) with repeated measures (age) and
218 including first order interactions and the error term. The single RI of an eye was

219 considered the experimental unit. Not significant interactions were deleted from the
220 model. The statistical significance and tendency were declared at $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.1$,
221 respectively.

222

223 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

224 *Determining the Matching Score Threshold*

225 The distributions of MS frequencies in the data set used to determine the sensitivity
226 in true positives and the specificity in true negatives of the technique are shown in
227 Figure 2. No images obtained during the training period (sessions 1 to 6, as later
228 indicated) were used to avoid the effect of operator training as recommended by Allen
229 et al. (2008) and Gonzales-Barron et al. (2008).

230 True negatives showed a symmetric distribution and peaked at $MS = 55$, whereas
231 true positives showed a left skewed distribution reaching the highest frequency at $MS =$
232 100 , indicating that both distributions were distinct and slightly overlapped. Allen et al.
233 (2008) indicated that the suitable threshold varies according to the nature of the forensic
234 application chosen. In our case, the use of RI as the auditing technology for verifying
235 lamb identity implies to discriminate between true and false matches at a stringent level.
236 From the resulting non-parametric ROC curve obtained in our results (Figure 3), the
237 cut-off or threshold MS value estimated to minimize the false matching error and the
238 false non-matching error in order to accept or reject a claimed identity, was $MS = 70$.
239 Estimated false matching error rate for this threshold was 0.5%, while the estimated
240 false non-matching error rate was 1.1%. As a result, the specificity and sensitivity
241 values obtained were 0.995 and 0.989, respectively. This 99.5% accuracy for verifying
242 lamb identity was considered adequate for minimizing the false positives in sheep
243 traceability in practice, being the value greater than obtained in previous

244 implementation studies in which molecular markers were used for auditing lamb
245 traceability (Caja et al., 2007).

246 Our obtained value of MS threshold agreed with that reported by Gonzales-Barron et
247 al. (2008; MS = 70) in adult sheep, despite the difference in age with our lambs,
248 although their specificity and sensitivity values were 0.992 and 0.998, respectively.
249 Allen et al. (2008) graphically chose an inspection threshold of MS = 75 in cattle of
250 different ages, but no specificity and sensitivity data were calculated.

251

252 *Matching Score Data Treatment*

253 A careful examination of the data set showed an inflated distribution of values at MS
254 = 100. This fact was a consequence of the matching algorithm used by the Optibrand
255 Data Management Software which was designed for a high throughput (approximately
256 20 pair matches/min). Although the exact algorithm used in this software is unknown,
257 the most plausible explanation was that each image was partially analyzed at the
258 beginning of the process and, if the agreement was satisfactory, the algorithm finalized
259 the calculations and attributed a MS = 100. Otherwise, the algorithm would continue
260 analyzing the RI and give an estimated and specific MS value. Consequently, this
261 algorithm provided inflated MS values of 100, with a non equal probability (nonzero
262 probability) and we decided to use the one-inflated bivariate Beta distribution, and to
263 build a specific model for the treatment of MS data from RI as proposed previously by
264 Puig et al. (2009) and detailed in the Appendix.

265

266 *Training Period*

267 Using MS and CT values as decision criteria, the training period was considered as
268 completed when the MS reached a plateau ($P > 0.05$; Figure 4); simultaneously the

269 operator achieved the image collection proficiency stated in the Optibrands benchmarks
270 of 1min per eye, on average. This occurred after the 6th training session ($MS = 93.2 \pm$
271 1.5 ; $CT = 91.3 \pm 15.8$ s) in which the RI of both eyes of a total of 66 lambs (33 lambs of
272 each breed) were collected in duplicate (264 images in total).

273 Operator training has been shown to be a key factor for collecting quality RI using
274 the OptiReader device (Whittier et al., 2003; Allen et al., 2008), although no
275 experimental data has been reported to show the differences between untrained and
276 trained operators. Allen et al. (2008) and Gonzales-Barron et al. (2008) proposed a 2 to
277 3 wk period of training which agreed with the results of our study if 3 half-day sessions
278 per week were carried out.

279 Values of MS during the considered training period (sessions 1 to 6) ranged between
280 90.1 and 93.4 (i.e., 3-mo Lacaune lambs and untrained operator in Table 1), being on
281 average lower than the rest of the MS data sets used (Table 1; $P < 0.01$). No eye side or
282 breed effects were detected during the training period ($P > 0.05$).

283 A progression of operator skill was observed from 1 to 6 sessions with increased
284 proficiency for collecting RI of acceptable quality and a CT reduction. Capturing time
285 decreased logarithmically ($y = 61.9 \ln x + 200$; $R^2 = 0.83$; $P < 0.05$) from 210 ± 50 s, at
286 session 1, to 53 ± 8 s, at session 7 ($P < 0.001$; Figure 4), but no differences were
287 reported thereafter ($P > 0.05$). On average, 2.6 ± 0.2 images were rejected until a RI of
288 acceptable quality was obtained, during the training period.

289 In contrast, CT during the training period ranged between 75 and 181 s and its
290 overall mean was longer than the means from other periods in the trained operator
291 (Table 3 and Figure 4; $P < 0.001$). In this case, an eye side effect was detected on CT,
292 the time required being lower for the right eye than for the left eye (Table 3; $P = 0.004$),
293 which may be a consequence of processing the left eye first according to our

294 methodology; the lamb being more stressed just after capturing and restraining. A
295 tendency was also observed by breed during the training period, the Manchega lambs
296 showing lower CT than the Lacaune lambs (122 ± 15 s vs. 164 ± 27 s, respectively; $P =$
297 0.054) which may be consequence of the greater age of the Manchega lambs to reach
298 the slaughter age.

299 Of the 132 pairs of RI compared in the training period, 127 pairs (96.2%) were over
300 the previously determined MS threshold ($MS \geq 70$) and were considered as being from
301 the same lamb. When eyes were analyzed separately, no differences in percentage of RI
302 over the threshold were detected between the left and right eye RI (97.0 vs. 95.5%,
303 respectively; Table 2; $P = 0.78$), allowing the left or the right eye to be used indistinctly
304 for verifying lamb identity.

305

306 *Intra-age Comparisons*

307 The MS values of the RI duplicates obtained from the same eye were intra-age
308 compared using the purged data set after excluding the training period images (sessions
309 7 to 16; 808 images). No differences by breed ($P = 0.69$) or between the left and right
310 eyes ($P = 0.98$) were observed for trained operator data and, consequently, their MS
311 values were pooled and the overall mean calculated (Table 1). Correlation between
312 values of MS for the left and right eye were extremely low ($R^2 = 0$ to 0.06 ; $P = 0.85$).
313 As a consequence, indistinct use of the left or the right eye may be done for verifying
314 lamb identity.

315 At 3 mo, the MS mean values for trained operator ranged between 94.4 and 97.9
316 across breed and eye. No breed or eye effect were detected ($P > 0.05$; Table 1). On
317 average, 98.8% of RI showed a $MS \geq 70$ (data not shown), which was a higher
318 percentage than the results obtained in the training period. With regard to CT, values at

319 3 mo were approximately half of those obtained in the training period, ranging between
320 37 and 83 s according to breed and eye (Table 3 and Figure 4). Left and right eye CT
321 values tended to differ ($P = 0.052$; Table 3), the interaction of breed \times eye being
322 significant ($P = 0.035$) and the Manchega lambs showing greater CT for the left than the
323 right eye. On average, 2.5 ± 0.2 images were rejected by the trained operator at 3 mo.

324 Comparison of RI at 6 mo of age showed similar MS results to those obtained at 3
325 mo of age; on average, 98.3% had $MS \geq 70$ (data not shown); no breed ($P = 0.89$) or
326 eye effects were detected in MS at 6 mo of age (Table 1; $P = 0.96$). Capturing time
327 continued decreasing according to the greater operator skill, and ranged between 27 and
328 42 s (Table 3; $P > 0.05$). Although the CT was lower in Manchega than Lacaune lambs,
329 the difference was not significant in this case (29 ± 3 vs. 38 ± 6 s; $P = 0.74$). On
330 average, 1.4 ± 0.1 images were rejected at 6 mo, showing an improvement of operator
331 skill (44%) from the 3-mo of age period.

332 Finally, at 12 mo of age, MS values steadied and were similar to those of 3 and 6 mo
333 of age (Table 1; $P > 0.05$), although the percentage of RI with $MS \geq 70$ reached the
334 highest value (99.1%). No differences by breed or eye were detected (Table 1; $P >$
335 0.05). With regard to CT at 12 mo of age, mean value was shorter than at 3 and 6 mo of
336 age and did not exceed 30 s per eye (Table 3; $P < 0.001$). As previously indicated, CT in
337 Manchega lambs were lower than in Lacaune (16 ± 1 vs. 26 ± 4 s; $P = 0.014$), this
338 difference between breeds being consistent across all periods but without an apparent
339 reason. Moreover, CT values of the right eye were lower ($P = 0.032$) than those of the
340 left eye, agreeing with the results obtained during the training period. The overall CT
341 obtained at 12 mo was markedly lower (21 ± 2 s) than reported previously by Rusk et al.
342 (2006; 56 s) and Gonzales-Barron et al. (2008; 50 s) in adult ewes, which agreed with
343 the low rate of rejected images for a RI of acceptable quality achieved in our data at 12

344 mo (0.7 ± 0.1 images), and a marked improvement of the operator skill was achieved
345 when compared with the 3-mo period (72%). Nevertheless, there is no information
346 available on the subjective criteria used by different authors for excluding or accepting
347 sheep RI at different ages.

348

349 ***Lamb Traceability***

350 Lamb traceability by artificial markers was assessed by calculating the retention rate
351 of ear tags and electronic mini-boluses. At the start of the experimental period, 2.8% of
352 the lambs had lost the official temporary ear tags (97.2% traceability). No losses of
353 electronic mini-boluses or permanent official ear tags, both applied at weaning, were
354 reported throughout the experiment, showing 100% traceability from weaning to
355 yearling under intensive fattening and grazing conditions.

356 Traceability auditing of lamb identity obtained from electronic mini-boluses or
357 permanent official ear tags data, was done by comparing the RI from the same lamb eye
358 at different ages and using the 3 mo of age RI as reference. Table 4 shows the 2 types of
359 inter-age comparisons done: 3 vs. 6 mo and 3 vs. 12 mo.

360 Obtained results showed that 8 (6.9%) and 7 (6.0%) RI comparisons by the
361 Optibrand software of 3 vs. 6 mo and 3 vs. 12 mo, respectively, failed to match at the
362 chosen threshold. The matching failure for the same pair of images was repeatable.
363 Nevertheless, visual verification of these images by 2 observers led to the conclusion
364 that these images were of high quality (contrasted vascular pattern, vertical and
365 horizontal alignments in relation to the screen guidelines, and without black edges,
366 glare, obstructions or blurriness) and came from the same lamb, and their MS values
367 were eliminated from the comparison, as reported in Table 4. This fact did not occur in
368 the intra-age comparisons. Although reasons for these false negatives were unknown,

369 we discarded that they were due to a RI deficient quality and we attributed it to an
370 incorrect overlapping made by the software. Further research on this issue is warranted.

371 Purged inter-age values of MS were, on average, lower than previously reported
372 intra-age values, ranging between 91.5 and 94.6 (Table 4). No breed, eye or age effects
373 were detected, being the last 93.5 ± 0.8 and 92.6 ± 0.7 , on average for 3 vs. 6 mo and 3
374 vs. 12 mo, respectively ($P = 0.43$). Mean MS values obtained in our results were
375 slightly lower than reported by Barry et al. (2008; 96.0), in lambs from 8 to 22 wk of
376 age, and by Gonzales-Barron et al. (2008; 95.6) in adult ewes under indoors conditions
377 which may be a consequence of a more restricted criteria of RI acceptance.

378 Despite the lower MS value obtained in our results, the RI inter-age comparison
379 made confirmed the 100% traceability of the lambs from weaning to yearling obtained
380 by the permanent official ear tags and the electronic mini-boluses.

381

382 ***Conclusions***

383 The use of retinal imaging was a useful technique for verifying the presumed identity
384 of live lambs from 3 to 12 mo of age. In order to accept or reject a claimed lamb
385 identity, the use of 3-mo retinal images as a reference and of a cut-off matching score
386 value of 70, provided enough specificity and sensitivity to achieve 100% traceability in
387 fattening and yearling lambs. No eye side and breed effects were detected in matching
388 scores. Nevertheless, an extra percentage of approximately 13% of pairs of images
389 considered by the software as not matching were false negative, so, we recommended
390 the visual checking of rejected pairs of images. Moreover, we detected an inflated
391 distribution of matching score values at 100, which seems to be a consequence of the
392 matching algorithm used by the data management software of the equipment, making

393 necessary the use of a specific model for the treatment of matching score data. No
394 mention to these facts was previously reported.

395 Under similar conditions to those used in this study, the use of retinal images is an
396 accurate technique for verifying the identity of living sheep, mainly overcoming the
397 retention and readability limitations associated with the use of identification devices.
398 Moreover, retinal imaging may be a real-time alternative to currently available
399 biomarkers needing to collect samples for laboratory analysis with the aim of auditing
400 the traceability of sheep.

401

402

LITERATURE CITED

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468

469

APPENDIX

470 An excess of matching values equal to 1 (MS = 100), not corresponding to the profile
471 of a continuous distribution between 0 and 1, were detected in the whole MS data set
472 used. Consequently, for analyzing these semicontinuous data, the one-inflated Beta
473 distribution and the one-inflated bivariate Beta distribution were used. The one-inflated
474 Beta distribution, defined over $x \in [0; 1]$ has a probability density function (**PDF**) of the
475 form,

$$476 \quad f(x; \mu, \phi, p) = p I(x) + (1 - p)(1 - I(x)) \frac{\Gamma(\phi)}{\Gamma(\mu\phi) \Gamma((1 - \mu)\phi)} x^{\mu\phi - 1} (1 - x)^{(1 - \mu)\phi - 1}$$

477
478

479 Here $I(x)$ is an indicator function, that is, $I(1) = 1$ and $I(x) = 0$ for $x \neq 1$. The right
480 part of this PDF, which corresponds to the classical Beta distribution, was
481 parameterized according to Ferrari and Crivari-Neto (2004). This model is equivalent to
482 the zero-inflated Beta distribution if each observation x is replaced by $1 - x$. We also
483 assumed that for $x \neq 1$, the corresponding population mean μ_i depended linearly on the
484 covariates by means of an appropriate link function like the logit. Then, in our data sets
485 we assumed that $\log(\mu_i / (1 - \mu_i)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Z_i$ where Z_i is a dichotomic variable indicating
486 the lamb breed (Manchega, 1; Lacaune, 2). The one-inflation parameter p_i was also
487 modeled in terms of μ_i to reflect the empirical fact that high values of μ_i are
488 accompanied by a high proportion of 1's. Thus, we assumed that $p_i = \mu_i^\gamma$, where γ is a
489 parameter to be estimated from the data.

490 For studying the inter-eye images, bivariate models were also considered. These
491 models have the special feature of the one-inflated terms. For instance, let (x, y) be the

492 two dimensional random vector that represents the MS observations from the left and
 493 right eyes of the same animal. The one-inflation phenomenon is more complicate for
 494 these bivariate patterns, because the 1's can appear in only one component or in both.
 495 The PDF of the one-inflated bivariate Beta distribution that we have considered can be
 496 written as follows:

$$497 \quad g(x, y) = \begin{cases} p_{11} & x = 1, y = 1 \\ p_{x1} f(x; \mu_x, c) & x \neq 1, y = 1 \\ p_{1y} f(y; \mu_y, c) & x = 1, y \neq 1 \\ (1 - p_{11} - p_{x1} - p_{1y}) f(x, y; \mu_x, \mu_y, c) & x \neq 1, y \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

498 Here p_{11} , p_{x1} and p_{1y} indicate the proportion of observations of the form (1,1), (x,1) and
 499 (1,y) respectively. Moreover, $f(x; \mu_x, c)$ and $f(y; \mu_y, c)$ are the PDF of the classical Beta
 500 distribution with population means μ_x and μ_y , and the same dispersion parameter c . The
 501 bivariate PDF $f(x, y; \mu_x, \mu_y, c)$ is just the PDF of the bivariate Beta distribution of Olkin
 502 and Liu (2003). It has the following expression,

$$503 \quad f(x, y; \mu_x, \mu_y, c) = \frac{x^{\frac{c\mu_x}{1-\mu_x}-1} y^{\frac{c\mu_y}{1-\mu_y}-1} (1-x)^{\frac{c}{1-\mu_y}-1} (1-y)^{\frac{c}{1-\mu_x}-1}}{B(\mu_x, \mu_y, c) (1-xy)^{c(\frac{\mu_x}{1-\mu_x} + \frac{\mu_y}{1-\mu_y} + 1)}}$$

506 More details can be found in Puig et al. (2009). For parameter estimation, we have
 507 maximized the corresponding log-likelihood function and the asymptotic standard errors
 508 were calculated from the Hessian of the log-likelihood at the maximum. With this aim,
 509 a program made in R was used and which is available from the authors upon request.

510

511 **Table 1.** Intra-age¹ comparisons of matching scores² of retinal image according to
 512 operator skill, breed (Manchega, Lacaune) and eye side (left, right) at different ages in
 513 lambs (values are means \pm SE)

Operator skill	Age, mo	Manchega		Lacaune		Overall
		Left	Right	Left	Right	
Untrained	3	92.5 \pm 1.9	92.5 \pm 2.2	90.1 \pm 1.8	93.4 \pm 1.7	92.1 \pm 1.1 ^a
		(33) ³	(33)	(33)	(33)	(132)
Trained ⁴	3	97.2 \pm 0.7	97.9 \pm 0.7	94.4 \pm 1.3	95.3 \pm 1.2	96.4 \pm 0.5 ^b
		(49)	(49)	(37)	(37)	(172)
	6	98.0 \pm 0.5	94.4 \pm 1.5	98.2 \pm 0.6	94.1 \pm 1.5	96.2 \pm 0.6 ^b
		(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(116)
12	96.9 \pm 1.1	95.8 \pm 1.8	96.1 \pm 1.0	96.5 \pm 1.0	96.3 \pm 0.6 ^b	
		(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(116)
	Overall	97.3 \pm 0.4	96.4 \pm 0.7	96.1 \pm 0.6	95.3 \pm 0.7	96.3 \pm 0.3 ^b
		(105)	(105)	(97)	(97)	(404)

514 ¹ Comparisons between image duplicates of the same lamb and eye taken at the same
 515 age.

516 ² Computed overlapping score of a pair of images (ranging from 0 to 100), obtained
 517 by the Optibrand's Data Management software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO).

518 ³ Values in parentheses are number of eyes studied.

519 ⁴ Training period images excluded. The operator was considered trained when only
 520 collected retinal images with matching score greater than 85 and the average time to
 521 acquire images was less than 1 min per eye.

522 ^{a,b} Within a column, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.01$). No
 523 differences between ages for the trained operator were observed ($P > 0.05$) and no
 524 effects of eye side, breed and their interactions were detected in all cases ($P > 0.05$).

525

526 **Table 2.** Percentage of retinal images showing matching scores¹ (MS) greater than the
 527 acceptance threshold (MS \geq 70) according to operator skill, breed (Manchega, Lacaune)
 528 and eye side (left, right) at different ages in lambs

Image comparison	Age, mo	Operator skill	Manchega		Lacaune		Overall	
			Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right
Intra-age ²	3	Untrained	97.0	93.9	97.0	97.0	97.0	95.5
			(33) ³	(33)	(33)	(33)	(66)	(66)
	3	Trained ³	100	100	97.3	97.3	98.8	98.8
			(49)	(49)	(37)	(37)	(86)	(86)
6	Trained ³	100	96.4	100	96.7	100	96.6	
		(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(58)	(58)	
12	Trained ³	100	96.4	100	100	100	98.3	
		(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(58)	(58)	
Inter-age ⁴	3 vs. 6 ⁵	Trained	100	100	100	100	100	100
			(27)	(26)	(30)	(25)	(57)	(51)
	3 vs. 12 ⁶	Trained	100	100	100	100	100	100
			(27)	(26)	(30)	(26)	(57)	(52)

529 ¹Computed overlapping score of a pair of images (ranging from 0 to 100), obtained
 530 by the Optibrand's Data Management software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO).

531 ²Comparisons between image duplicates of the same lamb and eye taken at the same
 532 age.

533 ²Values in parentheses are number of eyes studied.

534 ³Training period images excluded. The operator was considered trained when only
 535 collected retinal images with MS > 85 and the average time to acquire images was less
 536 than 1 min per eye.

537 ⁴Comparisons between images of the same eye and lamb, taken at different ages.

538 ⁵A total of 8 images were incorrectly declared unmatched by the software (false
 539 negative) and were excluded.

540 ⁶A total of 7 images were incorrectly declared unmatched by the software (false
 541 negative) and were excluded.

542 **Table 3.** Capturing time (s) of retinal images according to operator skill, breed (Manchega, Lacaune) and eye side (left, right) at different ages in
 543 lambs (values are means \pm SE)

Operator skill	Age, mo	Manchega		Lacaune		Overall	
		Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right
Untrained ¹	3	168 \pm 24 ^a	75 \pm 12 ^b	148 \pm 22 ^a	181 \pm 37 ^a	158 \pm 16 ^{ex}	128 \pm 20 ^{fw}
		(33) ²	(33)	(33)	(33)	(66)	(66)
Trained ³	3	66 \pm 10 ^a	37 \pm 6 ^b	83 \pm 14 ^a	75 \pm 12 ^a	73 \pm 8 ^y	53 \pm 6 ^x
		(49)	(49)	(37)	(37)	(86)	(86)
	6	27 \pm 3	30 \pm 4	34 \pm 6	42 \pm 9	31 \pm 3 ^z	36 \pm 5 ^y
		(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(58)	(58)
12	18 \pm 2 ^{ab}	14 \pm 2 ^b	30 \pm 6 ^a	21 \pm 4 ^{ab}	24 \pm 3 ^{ez}	18 \pm 2 ^{fz}	
	(28)	(28)	(30)	(30)	(58)	(58)	

544 ¹Corresponding to sessions 1 to 6 in which 264 retinal images were collected.

545 ² Values in parentheses are number of eyes studied.

546 ³Training period images excluded. The operator was considered trained when only collected retinal images with matching score greater than
 547 85 and the average time to acquire images was less than 1 min per eye.

548 ^{a,b} Within a row, mean values between eye and breed with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

549 ^{e,f} Within a row, overall mean values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

550 ^{w,x,y,z} Within a column, overall mean values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

551 **Table 4.** Matching scores¹ of retinal images compared inter-age² according to breed
 552 (Manchega, Lacaune) and eye side (left, right) in lambs (values are means \pm SE)

Age comparisons	Manchega		Lacaune		Overall	
	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right
3 vs. 6 mo ³	94.6 \pm 1.4 (27) ⁴	93.2 \pm 1.5 (26)	94.3 \pm 1.1 (30)	91.9 \pm 1.4 (25)	94.5 \pm 0.9 (57)	92.6 \pm 1.0 (51)
3 vs. 12 mo ⁵	93.7 \pm 1.3 (27)	93.7 \pm 1.2 (26)	91.5 \pm 1.3 (30)	92.5 \pm 1.2 (26)	92.5 \pm 0.9 (57)	93.1 \pm 0.8 (52)

553 ¹Computed overlapping score of a pair of images (ranging from 0 to 100), obtained
 554 by the Optibrand's Data Management software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO).

555 ²Comparisons between images of the same eye and lamb obtained by the trained
 556 operator at different ages. No effects of age, eye side, breed and their interactions were
 557 detected ($P > 0.05$).

558 ³A total of 8 images were incorrectly declared unmatched by the software (false
 559 negative) and were excluded. The failure was repeatable, but visual verification led to
 560 the conclusion that they came from the same lamb.

561 ⁴ Values in parentheses are number of eyes studied.

562 ⁵A total of 7 images were incorrectly declared unmatched by the software (false
 563 negative) and were excluded. The failure was repeatable, but visual verification led to
 564 the conclusion that they came from the same lamb.

565 **Figure captions**

566

567 **Figure 1.** Left: Capturing a retinal image in a yearling sheep, restrained in a head locker
568 and under natural daylight conditions inside a barn, by using an OptiReader device
569 (CM, camera; ICC, image capturing controller). Right: Retinal images of left and right
570 eyes of 3 mo of age fattening lambs.

571

572 **Figure 2.** Distribution of matching score frequencies for true negative (correct non-
573 matching, ●) and true positive (correct matching, ○) in lambs after the training period.
574 Matching score was computed by overlapping pairs of images using the Optibrand's
575 Data Management software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO). The operator was
576 considered as trained when only collected retinal images with matching score greater
577 than 85 and the average time to acquire images was less than 1 min per eye (see Figure
578 4).

579

580 **Figure 3.** Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve obtained for matching score of
581 retinal images in lambs after the training period of the operator. Matching score was
582 computed by overlapping pairs of images using the Optibrand's Data Management
583 software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO). The operator was considered as trained
584 when only collected retinal images with matching score greater than 85 and the average
585 time to acquire images was less than 1 min per eye (see Figure 4).

586

587 **Figure 4.** Changes in matching score (●) and capturing time (○) values of retinal
588 images in lambs according to the experience accumulated by the operator across the
589 working sessions carried out. At each working session, done thrice a week, the operator
590 collected the retinal images of both eyes from 9.2 ± 1.1 lambs, on average. Matching
591 score was computed by overlapping pairs of images using the Optibrand's Data
592 Management software v. 4.1.3 (Optibrand, Fort Collins, CO). The dashed line
593 represents the session at which the operator was considered as trained. ^{a-h}Mean values in
594 the same series with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

595 **Figure 1**

596

597 **Figure 2**

598
599

600 **Figure 3**

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603 **Figure 4**

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